

D3.2 Initial Report on the Integration of the 5G Experimentation Platform

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5g-iana.eu

Authors

Authors in alphabetical order		
Name	Organisation	Email
Matteo Andolfi	Nextworks	m.andolfi@nextworks.it
Edoardo Bonetto	LINKS	edoardo.bonetto@linksfoundation.com
Georgios Drainakis	ICCS	giorgos.drainakis@iccs.gr
Manuel Fuentes	Fivecomm	manuel.fuentes@fivecomm.eu
Luka Koršič	ININ	luka.korsic@iinstitute.eu
Miriam Ortiz	Fivecomm	miriam.ortiz@fivecomm.eu
Rudolf Sušnik	ININ	rudolf.susnik@iinstitute.eu
Markus Wimmer	Nokia	markus.wimmer@nokia.com
Thanos Xirofotos	UBITECH	txirofotos@ubitech.eu
Peter Zidar	Telekom Slovenije	peter.zidar@telekom.si

Control sheet

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Reviewer 1	Matteo Andolfi	25/08/2023
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Reviewer 3	Manuel Fuentes	29/08/2023

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
3GPP	3 rd Generation Partnership Project
5GC	5G Core
5GS	5G System
5G-PPP	5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership
5QI	5G QoS Identifier
AF	Application Function
AGV	Automated Guided Vehicle
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AMF	Access and Mobility Management Function
AN	Access Network
AO	Application Orchestrator
AOEP	Automotive Open Experimental Platform
API	Application Programming Interface
BLER	Block Error Rate
CI/CD	Continuous Integration and Continuous Deployment
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CU	Centralized Unit
DL	Downlink
DML	Distributed Machine Learning
DMLO	Distributed Machine Learning Orchestrator
DN	Data Network
DNN	Data Network Name
DNS	Domain Name Service
EC	European Commission

eCPRI	enhanced Common Public Radio Interface
eMBB	enhanced Mobile Broadband
EU	European Union
E-UTRA	Evolved Universal UMTS Terrestrial Radio Access
FDD	Frequency Division Duplex
FR	Frequency Range
FTP	File Transfer Protocol
GiB	Gigabyte
gNB	next generation NodeB
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GBR	Guaranteed Bit Rate
GPU	Graphical Processing Unit
gRPC	google Remote Procedure Call
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HDD	Hard Disk Drive
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
HW	Hardware
ICMP	Internet Control Message Protocol
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IP	Internet Protocol
ITS	Intelligent Transport Systems
k8s	Kubernetes
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KVM	Kernel-based Virtual Machine
LCM	Life Cycle Management

LTE	Long Term Evolution
M2M	Machine to Machine
MANO	Management and Orchestration
MB	Megabyte
MCC	Mobile Country Code
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
ML	Machine Learning
mMTC	massive Machine Type Communications
NF	Network Function
NIC	Network Interface Card
NSI	Network Slice Instance
MNC	Mobile Network Code
MNO	Mobile Network Operator
MSSQL	Microsoft Structured Query Language
MySQL	My Structured Query Language
NIC	Network Interface Controller
NF	Network Function
NGBR	Non-Guaranteed Bit Rate
NR	New Radio
NSA	Non-Standalone
RSRP	Reference Signal Received Power
RSRQ	Reference Signal Received Quality
RSSI	Received Signal Strength Indicator
OBU	On Board Unit
OS	Operating System
PC	Personal Computer

PDU	Packet Data Unit
PLMN	Public Land Mobile Network
PU	Public
qMON	Quality Monitoring System
QFI	QoS Flow Identifier
QoS	Quality of Service
RAM	Random Access Memory
RAN	Radio Access Network
RPi	Raspberry Pi
RSU	Road Side Unit
RTK	Real-Time Kinematic
SA	Standalone
SD	Slice Differentiator
SD card	Secure Digital card
SIM	Subscriber Identity Module
SM	Slice Manager
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
SMF	Session Management Function
SNIR	Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise Ratio
S-NSSAI	Network Slice Selection Assistance Information
SR	Scheduling Request
SSD	Solid State Drive
SSH	Secure Shell (or Secure Socket Shell)
SST	Slice/Service Type
SW	Software
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol

TDD	Time Division Duplex
TOPS	Trillions of Operations Per Second
TTI	Transmission Time Interval
TX	Transmit(ter)
UC	Use Case
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
UL	Uplink
UMTS	Universal Mobile Telecommunications System
UPF	User Plane Function
URLLC	Ultra Reliable Low Latency Communications
USB	Universal Serial Bus
V2X	Vehicle to Everything
vCPU	virtual CPU
vda	virtual disk array
vdb	volumetric data blocks
VNF	Virtual Network Function
vOBU	virtual On-Board Unit
VPN	Virtual Private Network
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

System integration is the process that connects one or more pieces of physical and virtualized hardware, as well as software components to create a single usable system, and the objective of this deliverable is to provide the system integration status of the 5G-IANA experimentation platform.

The document is structured in two major sections, with one chapter focusing on the integration activities in the Nokia and Telekom Slovenije 5G Systems, and another chapter highlighting integration activities of the 5G-IANA Experimentation Platform.

The Nokia Testbed in Ulm and the Telekom Slovenije in Ljubljana have been set up to run the use cases of the 5G-IANA project as planned for cycle A testing and to serve 3rd party experimenters. The described setup involves the deployment, configuration and testing of multiple sub-systems and components including the radio access network (e.g., radio frequency configuration), the user equipment (e.g., 5G modems and SIM cards), and the network core. Network slices have been pre-configured and tested so as to enable the appropriate network resource allocation; their configuration has included slice identifiers, 5QIs, radio interface quotas, etc. Servers to host the 5G-IANA platform and the Edge Servers have been acquired, configured according to the needs of the 5G-IANA project, and integrated in the testbeds i.e., the appropriate network configuration has been applied to enable the secure network connectivity of the 5G-IANA platform components both towards the 5GS and the Edge Servers for nApp management and orchestration purposes (and the clear separation against data plane/application traffic). All 5G-IANA platform components, namely - Catalogue, Composer, Application Orchestrator (AO), Slice Management (SM) & Resource Orchestration, Monitor, and DMLO - have been deployed on adequately dimensioned virtual machines on top of the aforementioned servers. The 5G-IANA platform integration has been further extended with the inclusion of GitLab server functionality for the support of nApp development, integration, and deployment through the means of version control, as well CI/CD functionality. Special attention has been paid to the system integration of OBUs and RSUs so as to become available as Far Edge nodes subject to 5G-IANA platform operations e.g., application function (AF) lifecycle management. Efforts in this case have focused on the functional integration of communication (i.e., 5G modem, UE) and computing components (e.g., CPU/GPU). Subsequently, containerized nApps can be deployed on OBUs, RSUs, and Edge servers.

All 5G-IANA platform virtual machines are networked and can be remotely accessed by all 5G-IANA partners and selected 3rd parties, in a secure manner, through appropriately configured VPN tunnels. This has been an essential part of the overall system integration/configuration, as it allows both continued development of the 5G-IANA platform components on the 5G-platform, as well as nApp continuous development and deployment, that is expected to facilitate 3rd party experimenters.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. 5G-IANA concept and approach

5G-IANA aims at providing an open 5G experimentation platform, on top of which third-party experimenters, i.e., SMEs in the automotive vertical sector will have the opportunity to develop, deploy and test their services. The provided automotive Open Experimentation Platform (AOEP) is a set of hardware and software resources that provides the computational and communication/transport infrastructure as well as the management and orchestration components, coupled with an enhanced nApp Toolkit tailored to the automotive sector, for simplifying the design and onboarding of new nApps. 5G-IANA exposes to experimenters secured and standardized Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) for facilitating all the different steps towards the production stage of a new service. 5G-IANA targets different virtualization technologies integrating different Management and Orchestration (MANO) frameworks for enabling the deployment of end-to-end network services across different segments (vehicles, road infrastructure, Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) nodes and cloud resources). 5G-IANA nApp toolkit is linked with an automotive Virtual Network Functions (VNFs) Repository including an extensive portfolio of ready-to-use and openly accessible automotive-related VNFs and nApp templates, that are available for SMEs to use and develop new applications. Finally, 5G-IANA develops a Distributed Machine Learning (DML) framework, that provides functionalities for simplified management and orchestration of collections of Machine Learning (ML) service components and thus, allows ML-based applications to penetrate the automotive world, due to its inherent privacy-preserving nature. 5G-IANA will be demonstrated through seven automotive-related use cases in two 5G Stand Alone (SA) testbeds. Moving beyond technological challenges, and exploiting input from the demonstration activities, 5G-IANA will identify and validate market conditions for innovative, yet sustainable business models for the AOEP platform, supporting a long-term roadmap towards the pan-European deployment of 5G as a key advanced automotive services enabler.

1.2. Purpose of the deliverable

System integration is the process that connects one or more pieces of physical and virtualized hardware, as well as software components to create a single usable system.

The objective of this deliverable is to provide the system integration status of the 5G-IANA experimentation platform.

The deliverable has the following structure:

Section 2 describes preparations done in the Nokia and Telekom Slovenije 5G Systems to provide stable and reliable 5G SA connectivity for a range of automotive services to be deployed on the 5G-IANA experimentation platforms. The activities included:

- the provision of latency optimised 5G V2X and eMBB network slices (Nokia testbed only),
- the provision of a testing site and the on-site 5G network capabilities,
- intensive testing of 5G smartphones and 5G modems to ensure their operativeness, and
- partners' support related to any connectivity problems to the 5G System.

Section 3 is organized around the main 5G-IANA experimentation platforms: the GitLab Servers (section 3.1), the 5G-IANA Platform Servers (section 3.2), the EDGE Servers (section 3.3), the Far-Edge Devices (section 3.4), and tools additionally used (currently only qMON, section 3.5). For each used 5G-IANA component a virtual machine was installed with the required system resources. The networking of the virtual machines for the 5G-IANA components is described in section 3.6.

1.3. Intended audience

The dissemination level of D3.2 is 'public' (PU) and available to members of the consortium, the European Commission (EC) Services and those external to the project. This document is intended to serve as a report on the 5G-IANA integration progress. Third parties can use the document to learn more about the integration of the 5G-IANA platform in mobile communication networks.

2. 5G SYSTEM INFRASTRUCTURE

5G has been introduced within Release 15 of the 3GPP specifications, following the introduction of 4G or Long Term Evolution (LTE) years earlier within Release 8. For 5G, a new radio interface solution called 5G New Radio (5G NR) was specified in close alignment with LTE radio solution Evolved UMTS Terrestrial Radio Access (E-UTRA) to allow a smooth interworking between the 4th and 5th generation mobile communication system and a smooth evolution from the older to the newer system.

Figure 1: the 5G System (5GS)

A **5G System** (5GS) is defined as a mobile communication system which consists of a 5G Access Network (AN), a 5G Core Network (5GC) and a User Equipment (UE), as shown in Figure 1. In more detail:

- A 5G Core Network (5GC) connects the 5G AN with Data Networks (DNs) such as the Internet or application servers. The task of a 5GC is to grant subscribers access to the communication services they are entitled to use. Functions realised are among others user authentication, provision of subscriber profile information, mobility management, connection management, and policy enforcement. 3GPP defined a set of network functions (NFs) for the 5GC with which it can provide network services to subscribers with a wide range of Quality of Service (QoS). Three of the NFs defined for the 5GC are outlined in the bullet points below, which are more frequently mentioned in the 5G-IANA project.
 - The User Plane Function (UPF) is responsible for routing and forwarding user plane packets – i.e. user data – between the 5G AN and external data networks with the QoS specified per data flow.
 - The Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF) is a control plane function – i.e. a management function – within the 5G Core Network. Its central responsibilities include the registration, connection management, and mobility management of users.

- The Session Management Function (SMF) is a control plane function, which manages the PDU session – i.e. connections with their associated QoS – allocates IP addresses, etc. based on the available network resources.
- The 5G Access Network (5G AN) is a radio access network which consists of Next Generation Node Bs (gNB). A radio access network is responsible for the radio resource management, which includes resource allocation to users according to their subscription profile, to hand over mobile subscribers between cells, to forward control plane data between the 5GC and the UEs, etc. UEs can be connected standalone to either 5G NR or E-UTRA, or with one radio technology acting as an anchor and the second radio technology as extension.
- A User Equipment (UE) allows a user to access mobile network services. Example of UEs are smartphones and radio modules. The interface between the UE and the network is the radio interface Uu.

A **5G System** (5GS) is defined to support two architectures:

- The Non-Standalone (NSA) architecture uses an upgraded 4G Core Network connected to LTE and 5G base stations. This makes both LTE and 5G NR available, but the types of connections which can be established between a UE and external DNs are restricted to the LTE core network features and capabilities.
- The Standalone (SA) architecture connects Next Generation Base Stations (gNB) to a 5G Core Network (5GC), which was designed with the objective to provide virtual networks to groups of users with requirements for enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), Ultra Reliable Low Latency Communications (URLLC), massive Machine Type Communications (mMTC) and Vehicular to Everything (V2X, from 3GPP Release 16 onwards).

5G-IANA aims to use some capabilities provided by the 5G SA architecture.

One key feature of 5G SA is **Network Slicing** that enables the multiplexing of virtualized and independent logical networks on the same physical network infrastructure. Each network slice is an isolated end-to-end network tailored to fulfil diverse requirements requested by a particular application (quoted from [4]). A Network Slice includes resources from the Core and Access Network.

A Network Slice is identified by its Single Network Slice Selection Assistance Information (S-NSSAI) identifier which is a concatenation of a Slice/Service Type (SST) and a Slice Differentiator (SD) identifier. The SST points to the expected Network Slice behavior in

terms of supported features and network functions optimisations. Currently, there exist 4 standardized SSTs, such as

- SST value 1 identifying an eMBB slice, or
- SST value 4 identifying a V2X slice (specified with 3GPP REL 16).

The operator can also deploy multiple Network Slices delivering exactly the same features but for different groups of UEs, e.g. as they deliver a different committed service and/or because they are dedicated to a customer, in which case such Network Slices may have e.g. different S-NSSAIs with the same Slice/Service Type but different Slice Differentiators (SDs) (cited from [2], section 5.15.1, see also [3] and [4]). The Subscription Information contains one or more S-NSSAIs.

Edge Computing enables operator and 3rd party services to be hosted close to the UE's access point of attachment, so as to achieve an efficient service delivery through the reduced end-to-end latency and load on the transport network. The 5G Core Network selects a UPF close to the UE and executes the traffic steering from the UPF to the local Data Network via a N6 interface (cited from [2], section 5.13). Servers used for Edge Computing are called EDGE Servers or Multi-access Edge (MEC) Servers. From the 5G System point of view, a server or servers hosting edge computing resources represent and are identified as external Data Networks (DNs), as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: PDU Session and QoS Flows

The 5G QoS model is based on QoS Flows. The QoS Flow is the finest granularity of QoS differentiation in the PDU Session. A QoS Flow ID (QFI) is used to identify a QoS Flow in the 5G System. User Plane traffic with the same QFI within a PDU Session receives the same traffic forwarding treatment (e.g.: scheduling, admission threshold) (cited from [2], section 5.7.1.1, see also [3] and [4]). For each QoS Flow, the QoS profile includes the 5G QoS Identifier (5QI), which is associated with characteristics on how to forward packets between the UE and the UPF. Following performance characteristics are defined:

- Resource Type (Guaranteed Bit Rate (GBR), Delay critical GBR, or Non-GBR);
- Priority Level;
- Packet Delay Budget;

- Packet Error Rate;
- Averaging window (for GBR and Delay-critical GBR resource type only);
- Maximum Data Burst Volume (for Delay-critical GBR resource type only).

2.1. Nokia Testbed

This section outlines activities in the Nokia 5GS to ensure the integration and testing of the 5G-IANA platform. The available radio frequencies, and their parametrisation and optimisation to meet the KPIs of the 5G-IANA use cases is described in sections 2.1.3 and 2.1.4. Two network slices, one for V2X and one for eMBB services, were configured, and their properties are presented in section 2.1.5. Selected smartphones and 5G modules are intensively tested in the testbed, to ensure that mobiles are working in accordance with the specifications, but also to verify that the Nokia 5GS itself is working properly and to determine the network capabilities for the 5G-IANA project. KPIs such as UL and DL throughput rates and RTTs at the testing site are listed at the end of section 2.1.3. The key network configuration settings are summarized in section 2.1.8.

2.1.1. Nokia Network Overview

Nokia operates an LTE/5G test network in Ulm, Germany. The on-air testbed consists of four active antenna sites, shown in Figure 1. The antenna sites DRK Ulm, SWU Lager and SWU K1 are available for 5G-IANA, whereby especially the antenna site DRK Ulm is configured to serve the 5G-IANA Use Cases (UCs).

Figure 3: Antenna Sites of the Nokia Testbed

For the 5G-IANA project, the 5G Standalone (SA) architecture ‘Option 2’ is provided. The Option 2 architecture connects 5G base stations – known as next generation Node B or gNode B’s (gNB) – to a 5G Core.

- The 5G Core (5GC) is the heart of a 5G network. It provides capabilities for mobility management, routing, security, policy control, charging, and subscriber data management. The 5G core architecture is built using cloud-native technology including a 5G Service Based Architecture with a set of specified Network Functions (NFs), such as the Access & Mobility Function (AMF) and the User Plane Function (UPF).
- The gNB belongs to the 5G AN and is responsible for Radio Resource Management such as Radio Bearer Control, Radio Admission Control, Connection Mobility Control. It uses the New Radio (NR) interface Uu and the 5G signalling protocols to interact with the UE integrated e.g., in an Onboard Unit (OBU). The gNB is connected to at least one AMF (Access and Mobility Function) for access and mobility related signalling. The gNB is connected to one or more UPFs (User Plane Function) for user data transmission.

The four antenna sites of the Nokia testbed are connected with optical cables to the central unit of gNB which is located in the Nokia laboratory. The UPFs, which are responsible for routing and forwarding user data between the gNBs and the external Data Networks (DNs), are also located in the Nokia laboratory. So is the EDGE Server, on which Data Networks (DNs) for 5G-IANA use cases are hosted. The EDGE Server provides computing resources at the “edge” of the mobile network and close to the mobile user (see Figure 4). Due to the co-location of gNB, UPF(s), and EDGE Server, and the use of optical fibre between gNB and the antenna sites, the latency of user data traffic between an antenna site and the EDGE Server is below 1ms.

Figure 4: Simplified Network Topology of the u-plane in the Nokia testbed

All entities in the Nokia laboratory – the gNB central units, the UPF, and the MEC server – are connected via a switch, as shown in Figure 5. The user plane connections are provided via optical fibre. A switch provides connectivity to the control plane functions of the 5GC such as the AMF and SMF via a VPN connection, which are located and managed in Finland. The switch also provides connectivity to the Internet.

Figure 5: Ulm testbed layout - connectivity

2.1.2. EDGE Server Infrastructure

A server was provided which operates as EDGE Server and which meets the 5G-IANA use case requirements, as requested by the 5G-IANA project partners. Its capabilities are:

- CPU: AMD Ryzen 9 5900X (12 cores)
- GPU: NVIDIA RTX 3080 TI
- RAM: 128GB

- SSD: 2TB
- HDD: 8TB
- NIC: 2*10G SFP+
- OS: Ubuntu server 22.04 LTS

In- and outcoming VPN with static source IP-address from project partner premises is used to access the MEC-Server. The root rights are restricted to Nokia, i.e., any SW installation requiring root rights such as Kubernetes is done by Nokia. A VPN connection to the Nokia testbed has been provided to all 5G-IANA partners who requested it, which allows them to directly access and manage applications running on the EDGE Server.

On the HW, one virtual machine for an EDGE-Server has been installed. New installations and updates depend on progress within the project.

2.1.3. Radio Frequencies, Radio Capabilities and Testing Sites

The Nokia testbed uses radio frequencies owned by mobile network operators, which are granted to Nokia for a limited period of time for testing and experimentation purposes. At the beginning of the 5G-IANA project, Nokia was still granted the use of frequencies in the 700MHz range (band n28), which provided excellent coverage with good throughput rates, as well as frequencies in the 3.6 GHz range (band n78), which provide high throughput rates with limited coverage. Due to the commercial roll-out of 5G in the city of Ulm, those frequencies are now used by mobile operators and are no longer available for the Nokia testbed.

However, three mobile operators granted Nokia the use of frequency resources in band n38. The antenna sites DRK Ulm was rebuilt at the end of 2022 to support band n38, while the reconstruction of the antenna sites SWU Lager and SWU K1 was completed at the end of Q2/2022. In all sites, three sector cells support operation in band n38.

The cell sectors operate in the frequency range from 2575-2615MHz (40MHz in the band n38 resp. band b41). In this frequency range, Time Division Duplex (TDD) must be used, i.e., two-way (= duplex) communication is realized by allowing the communication from the UE to the mobile network (Uplink, UL) and the communication from the mobile network to the UE (Downlink, DL) on the 40MHz frequency range at different time periods. The UL/DL split is 30/70, granting 30% of the radio resources for UL communication and 70% for DL communication. As fallback option, an UL/DL split of 20/80 can be configured. The parameter configuration and optimization is an iterative

process to meet the requirements of individual use cases. Figure 6 shows as example the improvement of the average round-trip-time (RTT) measured with 7 UEs at fixed installed locations as a consequence of continuous parameter optimization to meet the latency requirements for the 5G-IANA use cases. (The UEs are labelled SPU0 to SPU7 in the figure.)

Figure 6: average latency before and after parameter optimization

Figure 7 shows two sector cells of antenna site DRK Ulm and approximately the coverage of each sector. For use case testing an enclosed parking area close to the antenna site DRK and therefore with good radio conditions can be reserved. The reservation will be only possible at weekends (Saturdays and Sundays).

Figure 7: two sector cells of antenna site DRK Ulm and the parking lot available for trials

Figure 8 and Figure 9 provide the DL and UL throughput rates, which were measured with the smartphone One Plus 9 Pro and the tool G-NetTrack lite at and in the vicinity of the parking lot available for UC demonstrations and testing. Sector cell 2 is configured with 2x2 MIMO. An update to 4x4 MIMO is planned which can provide slightly better throughput rates. Please note that in comparison 5G radio modules may have worse performance values. The higher the frequency used for mobile communication, the smaller the coverage which can be provided, and the more volatile the throughput rate change for a moving subscriber. This can be clearly seen from the drive test in Figure 8 and Figure 9, and third party experimenters have to take these limitations this under consideration. At the parking lot available for UC testing and demonstration, a cell UL throughput rate of at least 7Mbps and a cell DL throughput rate of at least 100Mbps is supported. The RTT for PING is on average less than 20ms.

Figure 8: DL throughput in the vicinity of antenna site DRK Ulm based on a drive test

Figure 9: UL throughput in the vicinity of antenna site DRK Ulm based on a drive test

2.1.4. Radio Interface Configuration

The radio interface has the most significant impact on the latency in the data transmission between a UE and a UPF. In this section, four factors are outlined which impact the latency:

- the duplex transmission mode;
- the parametrization of the Scheduling Request (SR);
- the use of pro-active scheduling; and
- the setting of the BLER for uplink and downlink data transmission.

Duplex Transmission Mode:

5G NR uses two duplex communication modes:

- In Frequency-division duplex (FDD), downlink and uplink transmission operate using different carrier frequencies. For a transmission, there are carrier frequencies at any time available, and therefore a 5G network can theoretically allow a data block waiting for transmission to be transmitted immediately.
- In Time-division duplex (TDD), downlink and uplink transmission operate using the same carrier frequency, but at different time intervals. If for instance a data block is pending for uplink transmission, but the carrier frequency is used for downlink transmission, then the uplink transmission is at least delayed until the carrier frequency becomes available for uplink transmission.

FDD has therefore a slight edge over TDD with respect to latency optimization. The Nokia testbed operates on band n38, which requires the use of TDD.

Scheduling Requests:

If a UE is RRC_CONNECTED, and data is pending at the eNB for DL transmission, then the gNB can immediately send the data to the UE. However, if the UE is RRC_CONNECTED and if data or control messages are pending in the UE buffer for uplink transmission, and if no uplink resources have been granted to the UE, then the UE has to use the Scheduling Request (SR) for requesting uplink data transmission resources for new transmissions. The UE is configured with an SR configuration by the gNB. The SR configuration tells the UE among others when it can send the scheduling request and with which periodicity it can send a scheduling request. For instance, in case of sub-carrier spacing of 30kHz, where a slot length is 0.5ms, the 3GPP standards allows SR periodicities of 1, 2, 4, 8, 10, 16, 20, 40, 80 and 160 slots. If the SR periodicity is set to 80 slots (40 ms), then the UE can send a scheduling request once every 40 ms. In other words, the UE has to wait on average 20 ms before it can send a scheduling request. After sending the Scheduling Request, the UE has to wait typically at least 4 ms before receiving an UL grant, i.e.: a control message that specifies the radio resources the UE can use for uplink data transmission. The grant is used typically 4 ms after the reception of the control message. As a consequence, an SR periodicity set to 40 ms translates into an average delay of 28 ms before the UE can start UL data transmission. The Scheduling Request process is indicated in Figure 10. In the Nokia testbed, the SR periodicity is set to 40ms.

Figure 10: Scheduling Request process

Pro-active Scheduling:

Pro-active scheduling is a NOKIA specific network strategy, which reduces or even avoids the need to send a scheduling request (SR) by the UE. The eNB anticipates the UE's need of UL resources, which triggers UL grant allocation by the eNB (see Figure 11.)

For instance, ITS-messages and PING messages are sent in uplink direction by the UE. If the UE has been inactive for a prolonged period, then the UE must send a scheduling request to receive UL grants for UL data transmission. This triggers pro-active scheduling, which is continued until UE inactivity exceeds an operator set threshold. E.g.: if this threshold is set to 200 ms, but an OBU in the proximity of a crossing sends ITS messages at least once every 100 ms, then the UE in the vehicle can immediately sent the message.

Figure 11: Request-bases versus pro-active scheduling

In the test site,

- if pro-active scheduling takes place, the UE receives an UL grant every 4ms,
- the pro-active scheduling inactivity threshold is set to 1200 ms, and
- the UL grant allows the UE to transmit immediately at least 64 bytes. The granted Transport Block Size (TBS) size depends on the radio conditions. If a message is larger than the granted resource, then it will be segmented and transmitted consecutively.

Block Error Rate (BLER):

In mobile communication networks, the latency depends especially on the quality of the radio link, which is impacted by such as the signal strength (RSRP, Reference Signals Received Power) and signal quality (RSRQ, Reference Signals Received Quality). Dropping signal strength and quality leads to an increasing number of failed data transmission, resulting in the necessity to retransmit the data one or several times. If the used Transmission Time Interval (TTI) is 1ms, a retransmission of a data block on the radio interface occurs earliest after at least 8 ms. This delay is caused as the receiver notifies the transmitter about the failed transmission of the data block and asks for a retransmission.¹ Thus, dropping radio link quality leads to increased latency. This can be in part compensated by increasing the redundancy with which user data is transmitted via the radio interface, and by switching to a more robust modulation scheme. Increased redundancy reduces the probability of a failed transmission at the cost of increased demand of radio capacity for the data transmission. The probability that the transmission of a data block via the radio link is unsuccessful is called Block Error Rate (BLER). Commercial networks typically tune the BLER to 10% for the majority of end user services, and adjust transmit power, modulation, and user data redundancy (encoding) accordingly. Therefore, in the Nokia testbed, the same BLER value was set.

2.1.5. Network Slices

Network Slicing is used to allocate network resources to fulfil the requirements of specific services. The allocated network resources are isolated from other network slices to guarantee the quality of service needed for the specific services. Nokia provides two preconfigured network slices, as shown in Figure 12:

- One slice for Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB): eMBB is one of four standardized slicing options. Its prime use is for data-driven use cases requiring high data rates across a wide coverage area.
- One slice for Vehicular to Everything (V2X): V2X is another standardized slicing option. The long-term goal is to provide the V2X ecosystem and its players with

¹We ignore here 3GPP features such as “blind retransmissions”, in which the same data block is repeatedly transmitted one TTI after another without knowledge of the sender if the receiver has received one or several of the data blocks successfully. While this reduces the peak transmission delay significantly, it is also highly costly in terms of used radio interface resources, and therefore not used in commercial networks. Blind retransmissions are expected to be used especially for ultra-reliable low latency applications in Industry 4.0.

guaranteed low latency and ultra-high reliability even under high speed and conditions of high vehicular density.

eMBB is identified with the standardized Slice Service Type (SST) value 1 and V2X with the SST value 4. The use of standardized SSTs allows consistent slice provision and control among mobile network operators, which is especially important in the vehicular sector to ensure the same QoS for roaming users.

Figure 12: V2X and eMBB network slices in the Nokia testbed

For each slice has a default bearer with a specific QoS defined by a 5QI value.

- For the V2X slice, the default bearer has the QoS defined by 5QI value 179. The value 179 represents an operator specific 5QI value. Its QoS characteristics are similar to the standardized 5QI value 79. 5QI 79 was specified to meet the requirements for V2X messages.
- The default bearer for the eMBB slice has the QoS Profile specified with the 5QI value 7, which was specified for services such as voice, video life streaming, and interactive gaming.

The performance parameters associated with 5QI values 7 and 179 (in close alignment with 79) are provided in the Table 1. They are in line with the parameters as specified in [2], section 5.7.4, table Table 1.

5QI Value	Resource Type	Default Priority Level		Packet Delay Budget	Packet Error Rate	Default Maximum Data Burst Volume	Default Averaging Window
7	Non-GBR	70		100 ms	10^{-3}	N/A	N/A
179	Non-GBR	65		50ms	10^{-2}	N/A	N/2

Table 1: 5QI to QoS characteristics mapping

Each configured slice is associated with a Data Network (DN):

- The V2X slice provides connectivity to the DN identified with the Data Network Name (DNN) ulmas5qi79. The DNN will be translated with the help of a Domain Name Service (DNS) to the destination IP address of the DN.
- The eMBB slice provides connectivity to the DN identified with the Data Network Name (DNN) ulmas5qi7.

Each configured slice is currently configured for data transmission on the radio interface to meet following “quotas”:

- The V2X slice was configured for a minimum quota of 70% and a maximum quota of 100%.
- The eMBB slice was configured for a minimum quota of 10% and a maximum quota of 100%.

A minimum quota defines the percentage of radio resources per cell guaranteed for downlink data transmission. A maximum quota defines the percentage of radio resources per cell a slice can get if there is no demand for DL transmission resources by users of other slices.

(For uplink, similar results are achieved by setting so-called weight parameters.)

The impact of this radio parametrisation can be seen with following measurement example: Two co-located UEs were used, one connected to the high priority V2X slice (blue line) and one connected to the low priority eMBB slice (red line). In Figure 13: UL and DL throughput per slice, single UE deployment, only one UE is transmitting TCP packets, and the network allocates all available radio resources to the transmitting UE. As can be seen, both the UE connected to the V2X slice and to the eMBB slice realize the same downlink and uplink throughput rates.

Figure 13: UL and DL throughput per slice, single UE deployment

Next, the UE connected to the V2X slice, and the UE connected to the eMBB slice are served simultaneously. Both UEs again transmit with full buffer, i.e., they demand as much transmission resources as possible. Figure 14: UL and DL throughput per slice with one UE operating simultaneously per slice shows how the 5G network divided the cell's resources, granting at least 70% of the available resources to the V2X slice and at least 10% to the eMBB slice.

Figure 14: UL and DL throughput per slice with one UE operating simultaneously per slice

2.1.6. User Equipment (UEs)

5G Standalone is still a new technology and still not widely used. In order to determine suitable UEs for the use cases, intensive testing of UEs is required. Therefore, all UEs have to support the frequency bands, which were in the past and which are currently available in the Nokia testbed. UE testing is also used to check whether the network provides the configured functions.

5G smartphones are sold with an internally configured white-list, which specifies to which networks the phone is allowed to connect to. Mobile Networks are identified with a Public Land Mobile Network (PLMN) identifier, which is a concatenation of a Mobile Country Code (MCC) and a Mobile Network Code (MNC). The non-commercial Nokia testbed MCC is 262 and its MNC code is 731. As the Nokia PLMN identifier is not listed in the white-list

of commercial 5G Smartphones, they do not access the Nokia testbed. It is therefore necessary to overwrite the white-list in 5G Smartphones to make them operational in the Nokia testbed, which is currently only possible for the smartphones OnePlus 9 Pro and Nokia XR20 (see Figure 1).

Nokia XR20 operated stable under network configurations as tested at the time of this deliverable. OnePlus 9 Pro operates as well, but occasionally breaks down and then requires a factory reset and a renewed configuration to make it work again. The root cause of this problem has not been identified at the time being.

Figure 15: 5G smartphones Nokia XR20 (left) and OnePlus 9 Pro (right)

5G radio modules are deployed in OBUs and RSUs. Following 5G radio modules were tested in the testbed under different network parameter settings and proved to be suitable for a deployment:

- QUECTEL RM500Q-AE, and
- TELIT FN980 5G/LTE (see Figure 16).

When 5G radio modules are deployed, it is recommendable to check that the latest firmware is installed, which typically improves their operability and stability.

Figure 16: QUECTEL RM500Q-AE (left) and TELIT FN980 5G/LTE (right)

Various tests were conducted especially with the smart phone Nokia XR20 and 5G module TELIT FN980 5G/LTE to verify that access to the infrastructure, network slices, and subnetworks configured for 5G-IANA as described in section 3.6 in the Nokia testbed are working and are meeting the 5G-IANA project requirements:

	Nokia XR20	TELIT FN980 5G/LTE
Connectivity test with V2X slice		
Connection establishment	Successful	successful ⁽²⁾
PING	from UE to EDGE server: successful from EDGE server to UE: successful	from UE to EDGE server: successful from EDGE server to UE: occasionally not received by UE ⁽³⁾
Connection to Internet	Successful	successful
VPN connection to V2X subnet ⁽¹⁾	successful	successful
max. throughput and RTT	successful, target values reached	successful, target values reached
Problems and open issues	“Mobile data” switch off after a successful connection establishment, and then switched on, connection establishment fails. If then again “Mobile data” switch off and on, then connection establishment is successful.	
Connectivity test with eMBB slice		
Connection establishment	Successful	successful ⁽²⁾

PING	from UE to EDGE server: successful from EDGE server to UE: successful	from UE to EDGE server: successful from EDGE server to UE: occasionally not received by UE ⁽³⁾
Connection to Internet	successful	Successful
VPN connection to V2X subnet ⁽¹⁾	successful	Successful
max. throughput and RTT	successful, target values reached	successful, target values reached
Problems and open issues	“Mobile data” switch off after a successful connection establishment, and then switched on, connection establishment fails. If then again “Mobile data” switch off and on, then connection establishment is successful.	
Connectivity tests with two slices simultaneously: the V2X and the eMBB slice		
Connection establishment	fail; only one DNN can be set to which the smartphone connects to. This automatically restricts it to the use of a single network slice. All UCs in 5G-IANA using smartphones require only access to one slice.	successful ⁽²⁾
IP address allocations		Successful
PING		successful; simultaneous per network slice
Connection to Internet and subnets		successful; per slice as described above
max. throughput and RTT		50% of the UL resources allocated to V2X and to eMBB under high load per slice. No slice differentiation in UL for a single UE in the Nokia testbed.

⁽¹⁾ Subnets used for virtual machine networking is described in section 3.6 of this document.

⁽²⁾ The script `telit_qmi_connect.sh` executes `qmicli` commands.

⁽³⁾ It is under further investigation if there is a problem with paging or a too small packet discard timer being used.

Table 2: Operability of Nokia XR20 and TELIT FN980 5G/LTE in configured Nokia Testbed Network Slices

2.1.7. Subscriber Identity Modules (SIM cards)

A SIM card, also known as Subscriber Identity Module, is a smart card that stores information which links it with a subscription profile(s) stored in the home PLMN of the subscriber.

Nokia provides SIM-cards to enable access to the Nokia testbed for the sole purpose of testing and demonstrations, as required by the German regulator.

With a SIM-card, a user can either access the V2X slice or the eMBB slice or both.

For security and debugging reasons, each SIM card is associated with a unique static IP address (172.60.2.204 – 172.60.2.223) in 5G-IANA. The SIM card specific IP address is allocated to the UE once a PDP connection is established. (See also Figure 2.)

2.1.8. Network Configuration Setting

Table 1 summarizes the key network configuration settings, as described in the previous sections:

PLMN identification	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MCC • MNC 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 262 (Germany) • 731 (Nokia testbed)
Radio Network Implementation:	5G 3GPP Rel-15
Used band: (anchor) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • radio technology • duplex mode • subcarrier spacing • bandwidth • UL/DL split 	n38 (2.6 GHz, FR1) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5G NR • TDD • 30 kHz • 40 MHz • 30/70
TTI length:	0.5 ms
BLER:	10%
SR configuration: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SR periodicity: 	40 ms
Proactive Scheduling: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scheduling Grant frequency • Scheduling inactivity threshold • UL grant size 	activated on demand <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4ms • 1200ms • 64bytes
Connectivity: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transport technology: • Protocol: 	Remote radio head deployment with centralized unit (CU of gNB) in Nokia Lab <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Single Mode optical fibre • eCPRI
Core Network Implementation:	5G 3GPP Rel-15
5G architecture	5G SA

Connectivity <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transport technology (u-plane): • Transport protocol: • UPF connectivity to gNB: • Control plane functions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Single Mode optical fibre • GTP over IPv4 • direct link • remote (in Finland)
Network Slice Configuration	
V2X slice <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Slice/Service Type (SST) • 5QI • accessed DN V2X specific slice parameters <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • minimum prioritized quota • maximum prioritized quota Observed properties <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • avg. RTT to EDGE Server in low load scenarios 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4 (REL 16) • 179 (operator defined) • ulmas5qi79 • 70% • 10% • < 20ms
eMBB slice <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Slice/Service Type (SST) • 5QI • accessed DN V2X specific slice parameters <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • minimum prioritized quota • maximum prioritized quota Observed properties <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • avg. RTT to EDGE Server in low load scenarios 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 (REL 15) • 7 • ulmas5qi7 • 10% • 100% • < 20ms
tested UEs	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nokia XR20 • TELIT FN980 5G/LTE 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • works • works
MEC Implementation:	
Transport protocol: Connectivity to UPF:	IPv4 Direct link
Drive Tests:	
UE carried by pedestrian	

Table 3: Nokia Network Configuration Setting

2.2. Telekom Slovenije Testbed

2.2.1. Telekom Slovenije Testbed Overview

The Telekom Slovenije testbed was originally planned to only support indoor testing for UC7. For that purpose, Telekom Slovenije prepared a dedicated 5G infrastructure, which is located at Telekom Slovenije premises in Ljubljana (Research laboratory) at Telekom Slovenije headquarters in Ljubljana. During the project the partners identified risk that Nokia testbed may not be able to support many use cases therefore the backup plan was devised for Telekom Slovenije testbed to take over those use cases, if necessary.

Since UC7 is a simulated use case, the tunnel base stations, OBU, RSU and cross-border communication are only tested in a lab environment. Telekom Slovenije testbed originally supported only indoor cells and base stations. Due to outdoor nature of some of the additional use cases, which are considered to be tested in the Telekom Slovenije testbed, an additional outdoor environment is now examined to be part of the testbed as described in chapter 2.1.3. This environment will be covered with public base stations temporarily connected to dedicated 5G SA Core in Telekom Slovenije research lab.

A site-to-site VPN is configured between Nokia and Telekom Slovenije testbed. This private connection can be used for deployment of redundant components of 5G-IANA platform and tools in Telekom Slovenije testbed. The connection is needed for UC7 cross-border functionality testing but can also serve as additional way to quickly offer redundancy in case of any failures in either of the testbeds.

2.2.2. Network capabilities of the testbed

The Telekom Slovenije testbed contains a dedicated 5G infrastructure which is located at the Telekom Slovenije premises for the purpose of testing the 5G-IANA use cases. The dedicated 5G infrastructure is located at the location of Telekom Slovenije research laboratory and can be used only for the indoor demonstrations. For that purpose, Telekom Slovenije currently supports 3.5 GHz, although this can change based on 5G cell equipment available in the lab during the testing period.

The following table summarizes the 5G network capabilities:

Bandwidth DL	>300 Mbps
Bandwidth UL	>80 Mbps
Latency	<25 ms
Packet loss	<0.01%
Availability	>99.99%
Reliability	>99.99%

Table 4: Telekom Slovenije Testbed capabilities

Figure 17: Cisco UCS with 8 blade servers dedicated for 5G-IANA testbed at Telekom Slovenije

The infrastructure consists of:

- Cloud and virtualization environment - Cisco UCS with 8 blade servers and Wmware cluster installed, Centralized Edge (HPE ProLiant DL380 Gen10 8SFF Configure-to-order Server) as shown in Figure 17,
- Network connectivity,
- 4G - LTE radio access network (CA, Nb-IoT, VoLTE),
- 5G SA radio access network,
- 5G SA Core (HPE ProLiant DL360 Gen10 8SFF Configure-to-order Server)

Figure 18: Physical-level architecture of the Telekom Slovenije facility

2.2.3. EDGE Server Infrastructure

The cloud and virtualization environment (see Figure 18, number 1) is the main compute, storage, and network infrastructure of the facility.

It serves as a:

- container for deployment of virtual network functions (VNFs),
- for the control, management, and orchestration component (CMO) with Kubernetes and MANO support,
- if needed: 5G-IANA nApp Toolkit.

The Edge server HW specifications are:

- Intel Xeon-Gold 6240R (2.4GHz/24-core/165W) FIO Processor Kit for HPE ProLiant DL380 Gen10
- Intel Xeon-Gold 6240R (2.4GHz/24-core/165W) Processor Kit for HPE ProLiant DL380 Gen10
- HPE 32GB Dual Rank x4 DDR4-2933 CAS-21-21-21 Registered Smart Memory Kit
- HPE 1.2TB SAS 12G Enterprise 10K SFF (2.5in) SC 3yr Wty Digitally Signed Firmware HDD
- HPE Ethernet 10Gb 2-port SFP+ X710-DA2 Adapter

- HPE 96W Smart Storage Lithium-ion Battery with 145mm Cable Kit
- HPE Smart Array P408i-a SR Gen10 (8 Internal Lanes/2GB Cache) 12G SAS Modular Controller
- HPE Ethernet 10Gb 2-port FLR-SFP+ X710-DA2 Adapter
- HPE BladeSystem c-Class 10Gb SFP+ SR Transceiver
- HPE 800W Flex Slot Platinum Hot Plug Low Halogen Power Supply Kit
- HPE iLO Advanced 1-server License with 3yr Support on iLO Licensed Features
- HPE 1U Gen10 SFF Easy Install Rail Kit
- HPE Premier Flex LC/LC Multi-mode OM4 2 Fiber 15m Cable
- Graphic card: NVIDIA Tesla T4 16GB PCIe 3.0 x16

Figure 19: Components of 5G-IANA testbed at Telekom Slovenije

2.2.4. On-site Testing Options

Telekom Slovenije can provide suitable outdoor areas for the demonstration of the remaining use cases of the 5G-IANA project. The necessary public 5G mobile network infrastructure is available with an external 5G NR cell, which will be connected to the 5G SA core in its research lab. The location includes two parking lots at Telekom Slovenije premises (see Figure 20). All additional required equipment (cameras, OBU, RSU, cars, etc.) should be provided by the experimenters.

Figure 20: Telekom Slovenije, Vojkova 78, Ljubljana

2.2.5. Network Slicing

Slicing is currently not supported in any part of Telekom's 5G network. The version of 5G SA Core used for 5G-IANA is still under development and may not support all 5G functionalities.

3. 5G-IANA ENVIRONMENT

For an automotive application, a mobile network has to provide connectivity with a QoS required by the application. Otherwise, the mobile network is transparent to an application designer and an application user.

The 5G-IANA environment can be decomposed into five components:

- The GitLab Server: self-hosted platform that provides version control for software development in 5G-IANA.
- The 5G-IANA Platform: used for the development, orchestration, and management of nApps.
- The EDGE Server: provides Edge Computing capabilities which enable operator and 3rd party services to be hosted close to the UE's access point of attachment, and to achieve an efficient service delivery through the reduced end-to-end latency and load on the transport network.
- The Cloud Server: provides computing capabilities which enables operator and 3rd party services without strict end-to-end latency or transport load requirements to be hosted remotely. A Cloud Server deployment is not shown in Figure 21.
- The Far-EDGE devices: On-Board Units (OBU) and Road-Side Units (RSU) that provide connectivity to vehicles and roadside sensors.

Figure 21 shows the 5G-IANA servers and their interaction in case of a deployment in the Nokia testbed. In the Nokia testbed, there are the 5G-IANA Platform, the EDGE Server, and the FAR-EDGE Server(s). Individual companies can upload their software on the 5G-IANA GitLab Servers.

The red arrows identify data flows to administer the 5G-IANA infrastructure. Via the configured VPN connection, companies can access the 5G-IANA Platform, the EDGE Server, and the Far-EDGE Server and manage and supervise SW running on the respective devices.

When a user application is running, user data is exchanged between the Far-EDGE Server, the MEC-Server and the 5G-IANA Platform. These user data flows are shown with the blue arrows.

Figure 21: User data and 5G-IANA management flows

3.1. The GitLab Server

A GitLab server is a self-hosted platform that provides version control for software development projects. It allows multiple developers to collaborate on a project by providing a centralized repository where they can manage and track changes to the code.

One of the most important features of a GitLab server is the built-in CI/CD capabilities that allow developers to automate the building, testing, and deployment of their software projects.

3.1.1. GitLab

The 5G-IANA GitLab server has several capabilities that can be exploited in order to simplify the development process, improve collaboration, ensure code quality, and increase productivity for developers. The two principal features that the 5G-IANA platform provides are:

- **Version control:** GitLab server allows developers to easily manage and track changes to their codebase using Git. It offers features like branching, merging, and

code review, which help in collaborative development workflows. In the 5G-IANA platform, GitLab can be used by the open-source developers to provide the source code of their components.

- **CI/CD pipeline:** GitLab server provides built-in continuous integration and deployment capabilities. Developers can automate the building, testing, and deployment of their applications, ensuring code quality and faster delivery. In the 5G-IANA platform, this feature can also be used by the nApp developers to build their nApps and onboard them directly on the centralized registry.

GitLab, in addition, supports fine-grained access control, which allows administrators to define user roles and permissions for repositories. This ensures that only authorized individuals can access and modify the codebase. Thus, the developers should have a personal account on GitLab to access their specific repository and components.

3.1.2. GitLab Worker

A GitLab worker refers to a process responsible for performing various tasks or jobs in a GitLab instance. These workers handle background jobs, such as running CI/CD pipelines, sending notifications, performing code analysis, and running other tasks that require processing power and resources. They execute these jobs in parallel to ensure efficient processing and responsiveness in the GitLab environment. Workers often run on separate machines or containers to distribute the load across multiple resources.

Specifically, in 5G-IANA, GitLab workers are used to run the CI/CD pipelines. The 5G-IANA CI/CD pipelines specify to use the docker approach to run each step of the pipeline. For example, in the build step of a generic 5G-IANA CI/CD pipeline the `gcr.io/aniko-project/executor:v1.9.0-debug` is used to compile the Dockerfile available in the project repository, like assessed in [9].

The GitLab worker, as depicted in Figure 21, has a direct connection to the 5G-IANA NOKIA testbed, established thanks to a VPN connection between the two points.

3.2. The 5G-IANA Platform

The 5G-IANA platform is used for the development, orchestration, and management of nApps. The 5G-IANA platform consists of the following components, whereby for each component, the key tasks, integration status, and system requirements are described in the following subsections.

3.2.1. Hardware capabilities in the Testbeds

3.2.1.1. *Nokia Testbed*

In the Nokia laboratory, a server is deployed to host the 5G-IANA platform. In agreement to the requirements determined by the 5G-IANA consortium for the 5G-IANA platform, a server with the following capabilities was acquired:

- CPU: 2*Xeon® CPU E5-2680 v3 @ 2.50GHz 12 Core
- RAM: 128GB
- SSD: 1TB
- HDD: 1TB
- NIC: 4 optical, 2 electrical

3.2.1.2. *Telekom Slovenije Testbed*

In TS laboratory, a server will be deployed to host the 5G-IANA platform. A server with following capabilities will be available:

- CPU: 2 x Intel Xeon-Gold 6240R (2.4GHz/24-core/165W) FIO Processor Kit for HPE ProLiant DL380 Gen10
- RAM: HPE 32GB Dual Rank x4 DDR4-2933 CAS-21-21-21 Registered Smart Memory Kit
- HDD: HPE 1.2TB SAS 12G Enterprise 10K SFF (2.5in) SC 3yr Wty Digitally Signed Firmware HDD
- Network: HPE Ethernet 10Gb 2-port SFP+ X710-DA2 Adapter
- Graphic card: NVIDIA Tesla T4 16GB PCIe 3.0 x16

3.2.2. **Virtual Machines and Containerization**

3.2.2.1. *Nokia Testbed*

For each 5G-IANA component of the 5G-IANA platform listed in sections 3.2.3 to 3.2.8, and section 3.5, one Linux Kernel-based Virtual Machine (KVM) is configured. The resources allocated to each 5G-IANA component are listed in Table 4. On each virtual machine, the operating system Ubuntu server 22.04 LTS and Kubernetes are installed. The root rights are restricted to Nokia, i.e., any SW installation requiring root rights such as Kubernetes is realized by Nokia.

Hostname	CPU	Memory [GB]	NIC1	NIC2	vda [GiB]	vdb [GiB]
5g-iana-nApp	4	8	192.168.100.2	192.168.101.2	50	100

5g-iana-ao	4	8	192.168.100.3	192.168.101.3	50	100
5g-iana-dmlo	4	8	192.168.100.6	192.168.101.6	50	100
5g-iana-monitor	4	8	192.168.100.5	192.168.101.5	50	100
5g-iana-manager	4	8	192.168.100.4	192.168.101.4	50	100
5g-iana-taf	2	4	192.168.100.7	192.168.100.7	50	100
5g-iana-qmon-server	4	8	192.168.100.8		50	50
5g-iana-qmon-agent	2	8	192.168.100.9		50	50

Table 5: VMs capacities on 5G-IANA Nokia platform

The networking of the virtual machines and the access of the 5G-IANA platform is described in section 3.6. For further information on KVM, please refer to [5].

3.2.3. 5G-IANA Catalogue

The 5G-IANA catalogue is a software composed by two components: the Centralized registry and the nApp package Management, as shown in Figure 22.

Figure 22: 5G-IANA Platform

The **Centralized registry** stores and makes the AF/NF images available in 5G-IANA and provides various functions for storing and managing them. This registry offers a complete range of operations for storing, updating, and deleting 5G-IANA atomic components. By utilizing this registry, components can be easily reused in different scenarios with varying requirements.

The registry provides an interface to use for sending commands to it. The operations you can send are the typical docker operations:

- **Push:** You can push (upload) Docker images from the GitLab server (or your local machine, if able to connect with the 5G-IANA platform) to the registry using the docker push command. This makes the images available for others to download.

- **Pull:** You can pull (download) Docker images from the registry to the 5G-IANA composer (or your local machine) using the docker pull command. This allows you to utilize images created by others.
- **Search:** You can search for Docker images in the registry using the docker search command. This helps you discover and find relevant images for your specific needs.
- **List:** You can list the available Docker images in the registry using the registry's API or command-line tools. This provides an overview of the images stored in the registry.
- **Delete:** You can delete Docker images from the registry using the appropriate command or API call. This removes the images from the registry and makes them no longer accessible.
- **Tag:** You can assign tags to Docker images in the registry using the docker tag command. Tags help distinguish different versions or variations of an image.
- **Authenticate:** You can authenticate with the Docker registry to access private images or perform certain operations. Authentication ensures only authorized users can interact with the registry.
- **Manage access permissions:** Depending on the registry, you can manage access permissions to specify who can push, pull, or delete images. This helps control and secure the registry.

Of course, not all the operations are available to all the users; the developers and the normal 5G-IANA user can only do the first four operations. The others can be done by the 5G-IANA admin or automatically (like the TAG command, that is done automatically by the CI/CD pipeline).

The registry accepts connections on port 5000 and is linked to:

- the GitLab server to receive the push operations and the docker images provided by the CI/CD pipelines,
- the Composer to provide the list of available docker images already stored in the registry for creating a nApp.

The **nApp Package Management** instead is a Java application developed using the Spring Boot framework for Java. Spring Boot is an open-source framework that allows the creation of standalone and production-ready applications. The catalogue has two main interactions:

It works with the Vertical Service Composition and Customization component to compose new network applications or update existing ones.

It also interacts with the GitLab platform to store and onboard stable network applications.

The catalogue provides multiple APIs on the port 8082, that allow users to manage nApp packages from both the Vertical Service Composition and Customization component and the GitLab platform.

It is important to highlight that the components that make up the nApp Catalogue are crucial, but they do not require a heavy usage of computing resources.

The centralized registry, for a production environment has the following requirements:

- 16GB of RAM
- 4 vCPUs
- 25-100GB of free disk space

For the nApp catalogue, the requirements are even less:

- 8GB of RAM
- 2 vCPUs
- 25GB of free disk space
- minIO filesystem available to use
- postgresDB available to use

The components of the 5G-IANA catalogue are already deployed and are up and running on the NOKIA testbed. The components can be accessed by third parties that have a VPN connection with the NOKIA testbed.

The centralized registry is accessible at 192.168.100.2:5000.

The nApp catalogue is accessible at 192.168.100.2:8082.

3.2.4. 5G-IANA Vertical application Composition and Customization

The 5G IANA Vertical application composition and customization component or for brevity, Composer, is part of the nApp Toolkit and the aim of it is to assist the nApp providers wrap their applications in a format, so as to onboard and publish it in the nApp Catalogue (Section 3.2.3). It provides the capability to onboard and compose a valid nApp. The onboarding process is performed through a dedicated user interface which will offer several design-time features, in order to make the overall process less error-prone. The nApp composition process provides design-time validation for every nApp component and guarantees that properties such as metadata regarding minimum infrastructural requirements, metadata regarding deployment preferences, metadata

regarding configuration parameters during component initialization, mutable configuration parameters during runtime, exposed and required interfaces, etc. are maintained.

The nApp Composer communicates and stores the new graph to the nApp catalogue and provides input to the Vertical Application Deployment & Lifecycle Management (Section 3.2.5) before a deployment starts. Both communications are performed via REST.

The 5G-IANA Composer is written in Java 11 using Quarkus framework [11] for the backend parts. The tools and code languages behind the front-end parts (views and Gui) are React.js [12] and VivaGraph.js [13], while the features validating a new nApp graph during the composition phase are totally java-based.

To duplicate a deployment of the composer the requirements are:

- 8GB of RAM
- 2 vCPUs
- 25GB of free disk space

3.2.5. 5G-IANA Vertical Application Deployment and Lifecycle Management

The 5G-IANA Vertical Application Deployment and Lifecycle Management, which for brevity is called the **Application Orchestrator**, is comprised of three internal components, the Deployment Management and the Lifecycle Management and the Slice Intent Handler.

- The Deployment Management is the software module that carries out the task to perform the initial and actual deployment of a nApp graph on top of programmable resources by undertaking the task of communication with the underlying registered infrastructure. It communicates with the Resource Inventory (see section 3.2.6) to be fully aware of the available resources, and their state for the actual deployment.
- The Lifecycle Management runs in an infinite loop that starts after the initial deployment for of the nApp components. It assesses continuously the existing resources, the deployment requests and the reconfiguration requests. Lifecycle Manager is coupled with the Deployment Manager since it coordinates and handles the lifecycle management of each component, specifically the actions regarding the instantiation, termination and configuration, the collection of components'

data metrics, and provides information about the status of each component. In a nutshell, Lifecycle Manager is responsible to maintain the operational state of the nApp.

- The Slice Intent Handler handles the complete lifecycle of Network Slice creation. The lifecycle of a slice includes a) the slice request phase, b) the slice instantiation, c) the slice operation and d) the slice deprovision. Slice Intent Handler communicates with Slice Manager (see 3.2.6) to facilitate the appropriate slice formulation with the resource requirements each nApp demands.

The three components Deployment, Lifecycle Management, Slice Intent Handler are microservices that are developed in Java 11. The communication between the three aforementioned components happens through a Kafka [14] bus while the communication between Slice Intent Handler and Slice Manager through REST.

The deployment of the Application Orchestrator requires for deployment management:

- 2 vCPUs
- 3GB of RAM
- 5GB of free disk space

For Lifecycle Management:

- 3 vCPUS,
- 4GB of RAM
- 3GB of disk space

For Slice Intent Handler:

- 1 vCPU,
- 2GB of RAM
- 1 GB of disk

3.2.6. 5G-IANA Slice Management (SM) and Resource Orchestration

The components of the Slice Management and Resource Orchestration Layer were successfully deployed. In particular:

- The Resource Inventory: This component is responsible to keep the information about the availabilities of the Edge and Far Edge Resources;
- The App Quota Manager: The component responsible to manage the lifecycle of computing quotas and k8s namespaces allocated on the k8s clusters;
- The Slice Manager: The component to select the most suitable Network Slice within the list of available ones;

The Slice Management and Resource Orchestration layer is responsible for managing the available Network Slice Instances (NSIs) and validating Service Providers' requests for Vertical Services, ensuring compatibility with supported 5G service profiles. This layer also handles the arbitration, allocation, and provisioning of compute resources across the 5G-IANA distributed compute infrastructure. Additionally, it facilitates the subscription and continuous discovery of Far-edge resources (OBUs and RSUs), which may not always be online and available for executing services.

To achieve these functionalities, the Information & Localization service, together with resource orchestration services executed at the OBU/RSU and Edge hosts, collects relevant information about the status of the resource environment. This information enables the orchestration of Application Functions (AFs) and Network Functions (NFs) on top of the available resources.

The deployment of the Slice Management and Resource Orchestration component involves setting up the functionalities for managing Network Slice Instances, validating Service Providers' requests for Vertical Services, and orchestrating compute resources across the 5G-IANA distributed compute infrastructure, enabling efficient orchestration of Application Functions and Network Functions on top of the available resources.

The Slice Management and Resource Orchestration layer is composed of two software components, namely the Resource Inventory and the Quota Manager.

To deploy the Resource Inventory, the following specifications are required:

- vCPU: 2
- RAM: 4GB
- Storage: 10GB

Similarly, to deploy the Quota Manager, the following specifications are needed:

- vCPU: 2
- RAM: 4GB
- Storage: 10GB

With these specifications, both components can be set up to efficiently manage the available Network Slice Instances, validate Service Providers' requests for Vertical Services, and handle the allocation and provisioning of compute resources across the 5G-IANA distributed compute infrastructure.

The components are already deployed and are up and running on the NOKIA testbed. The components can be accessed by third parties that have a VPN connection with the NOKIA testbed.

The App Quota Manager component is accessible at 192.168.100.4:5100.

The Slice Manager is accessible at 192.168.100.4:8083.

The Resource Inventory is accessible at 192.168.100.3:8084 and 192.168.100.4:8085.

3.2.7. 5G-IANA Monitoring

Monitoring is responsible for the management of the metrics captured from the underlying virtualized infrastructure including the on-vehicle MANO and metrics from the deployed nApps. The monitoring metrics relate with resource utilization (e.g., compute, memory, network) and application-level metrics from the deployed nApps (e.g., throughput, active users). The Monitoring service enables core services (e.g., Orchestration, Policies, Analytics) and its implementation follows an agent-based architecture that embraces the producer-consumer paradigm. This approach provides interoperable, scalable, and real-time monitoring of both application and infrastructure behaviours, built on data extracted from both deployed nApps and the underlying programmable infrastructure.

The technologies behind the monitoring service are based on the Prometheus monitoring tool, which collects and aggregates the monitoring data from all monitoring sub-systems that have been developed (i.e.: active/passive KPIs at the application component and VNF KPIs). Some of the integrated data sources are:

Blackbox: enables probing endpoints using HTTP, HTTPS, DNS, TCP, ICMP, and gRPC. The integration of Blackbox with the monitoring enables collecting telemetries through different protocols.

Node Exporter: exposes a wide variety of hardware- and kernel-related metrics. These metrics are now part of the monitoring to provide insights regarding hardware and infrastructural aspects.

Kube-state-metrics is a listening service that generates metrics about the state of Kubernetes objects. This collection of metrics had been integrated with the monitoring to collect metrics regarding the Kubernetes entities.

Netdata: provides variety of metrics for hardware, containers, and applications. Netdata metric collectors are the “heavy gun” in the monitoring arsenal. The number of metric groups that can be enabled surpasses 40 and totals almost 2000 metrics.

The deployment of the Monitoring requires:

- vCPU: 4
- RAM: 12GB
- Storage: at least 70GB

3.2.8. 5G-IANA Distributed Machine Learning Orchestrator (DMLO)

The 5G-IANA DMLO module is comprised of three components: the DMLO backend, the DMLO frontend and a DMLO database. The design of DMLO's interfaces, data schemas and functionalities occurred during the 1st Cycle of the Project's Development Plan, while the implementation, integration, deployment, and validation has been scheduled for the 2nd Cycle.

DMLO Backend: A standalone web service handles all communications between the DMLO and the platform's components as specified in D3.1 [10], as well as DMLO's internal logic in regard to the management and orchestration of the far-edge nodes' computational tasks e.g., client/UE selection. The integration with the remainder of the 5G-IANA platform builds on the following interfaces:

- DMLO Backend-ResourceInventory: Periodic RESTful requests from the DMLO to obtain generic far-edge node statistics [10], such as node availability, computational capacity, storage, available memory, etc.
- DMLO Backend-DataCollection: Based on Prometheus monitoring mechanism, this interface allows the DMLO to collect computational task-specific qualitative and quantitative statistics [10], such as data availability, data staleness, etc.
- DMLO Backend-PolicyExecution: RESTful requests from the DMLO to dynamically apply an Application Function (AF) Life Cycle Management (LCM) event on a (computational) far-edge node level e.g., activate/ deactivate an AF container, depending on predefined input criteria.
- DMLO Backend-AggrNode (initial configuration): RESTful request from the DMLO that handles the initial setup of the AggrNode i.e, configuration of the Flower server for the respective Machine Learning (ML) task (number of training clients, ML hyper-parameters, aggregation algorithm, etc.)
- DMLO Backend-AggrNode (status monitoring): Periodic RESTful requests from the DMLO, to obtain the status of a Machine Learning task in a real-time manner. Relevant statistics include current ML loss and accuracy, number of dropped clients, round completion percentage, etc.

DMLO Frontend: Acts as the entrypoint of the DMLO module. It allows the user to configure the computational task that runs on the far-edge nodes e.g., client selection constraints, termination criteria, etc. In parallel, it exposes a Graphical User Interface (GUI) that enables visualization of the respective task monitoring statistics. The Frontend is designed as a standalone web service that only communicates with DMLO Backend in a RESTful manner.

DMLO Database: This component is attached to the DMLO Backend and serves as a data structure, where the obtained far-edge node statistics are (locally) saved. This enables faster processing in the DMLO Backend, minimizing the need to continuously query other platform modules for client information. The DMLO database is designed as a static tabular data structure.

To deploy the DMLO module, the following specifications are required:

- vCPU: 4
- RAM: 50GB
- Storage: 8GB

3.3. The EDGE Server

3.3.1. Hardware capabilities in the testbeds

The EDGE Server infrastructure in the Nokia testbed is described in section 2.1.2. and of the Telekom Slovenije in section 2.2.3.

3.3.2. Virtual Machines and Containerization

3.3.2.1. Nokia Testbed

One Linux Kernel-based Virtual Machine (KVM) is configured on the MEC-Server hardware. One virtual machine to host the DNs used in the 5G-IANA project is installed with capabilities as listed in Table 6. The operating system Ubuntu server 22.04 LTS and Kubernetes are installed on this VM. The root rights are restricted to Nokia, i.e., any SW installation requiring root rights such as Kubernetes is realized by Nokia.

Hostname	CPU	Memory [GB]	NIC1	NIC2	vda [GiB]	vdb [GiB]
5g-iana-mec	24	100	192.168.100.1	192.168.101.1	1000	7300

Table 6: VM capacity on the Nokia MEC Server for the 5G-IANA EDGE Server

The networking of the virtual machines and the access of the 5G-IANA platform is described in section 3.6.

For further information on KVM, please refer to [5].

3.4. The Far-EDGE Devices

The 5G Far-EDGE devices are the On-Board Unit (OBU) and the Road-Side Unit (RSU). The first one is used to provide connectivity to vehicles, enabling the deployment of nApps through the 5G-IANA platform on the vehicle-side. The RSU is mainly used to connect roadside sensors to edge and/or cloud services. The RSU can also host nApps deployed on the RSU through the 5G-IANA platform. For example, nApps that pre-process sensor data can be deployed on the RSU.

The 5G-IANA project is currently using two different OBUs provided by LINKS and Fivecomm, and a single RSU provided by LINKS. Furthermore, LINKS provides virtual OBUs that can be used for initial testing of nApps.

3.4.1. LINKS OBUs and RSUs

The OBU and RSU provided by LINKS are based on a carrier board that integrates an NVIDIA® Jetson Xavier™ NX board, which is an ARM64 embedded device equipped with a GPU. The technical specifications of this particular board are the following:

- GPU: 384-core NVIDIA Volta™ GPU with 48 Tensor Cores ensuring an AI performance of 21 TOPS.
- CPU: 6-core NVIDIA Carmel ARM®v8.2 64-bit CPU 6MB L2 + 4MB L3.
- Memory: 16 GB 128-bit LPDDR4x59.7GB/s.
- Storage: 16 GB eMMC 5.1.

Both OBU and RSU integrate a 5G Telit FN980 modem to provide connectivity through the Uu interface. Furthermore, they have an Ethernet interface to provide a connection to the vehicle network (in the case of the OBU) or to external sensors (in the case of the RSU). A WiFi hotspot is also available for enabling an interaction between the OBU and smartphones and RSUs with wireless roadside sensors. The OBU is also equipped with an Ublox F9P GNSS receiver supporting RTK corrections to provide accurate vehicle localization.

The first integration of these OBU and RSU into the 5G-IANA testbeds concerned the 5G connectivity. The 5G Telit modem was configured with the proper network parameters (e.g., APN) and it was successfully assessed that network connectivity through the 5G network was available. Further integration step was to make the far-edge devices part of the microk8s cluster. This has been done by performing manually the joining of the devices to the microk8s cluster. After this step, the devices were effectively part of the 5G-IANA Environment, and it was possible to deploy nApps on them using the 5G-IANA AO. Further integrations of the far-edge devices were the instantiation of the far-edge services required by the 5G-IANA Platform that are namely the “Information and localization” service and the “Resource monitoring” service.

Examples of the OBU and RSU with camera and LiDAR provided by LINKS for the 5G-IANA project are shown in Figure 23.

Figure 23: OBU (left) and RSU (right) provided by LINKS.

3.4.2. Fivecomm OBU

The second OBU provided by Fivecomm is integrated within one of the vehicles specifically used within the project, i.e., an Automated Guided Vehicle (AGV) also provided by Fivecomm. It is an OBU that comes with an Ubuntu distribution and the following technical specifications:

- GPU: Intel UHD Graphivs 630 (CFL GT2).
- Processor: Intel Core i7-9700 with CPU @ 3 GHz x 8.
- Memory: 32 GB.
- Storage: 983 GB.

This OBU permits the use of any 5G modem via Ethernet or USB to provide connectivity through the Uu interface. So far, two different types of 5G devices have been integrated together with this OBU and tested in the network provided by Nokia in Ulm, i.e., a 5G modem developed by Fivecomm, based on a Quectel RG500Q-EA module, and connected via Ethernet, and several 5G modems provided by Nokia, based on Quectel RM500Q-AE and connected via USB to the OBU. A Wi-Fi hotspot is also available for enabling the interaction of the OBU and a nApp user.

This second OBU has been successfully integrated into the 5G-IANA platform as well, configuring it as part of the microk8s cluster. As with the first far-edge device, this has been done by performing manually the joining to the microk8s cluster and integrating it as part of the 5G-IANA environment. This allowed Fivecomm to deploy nApps and perform a first validation of the component in Ulm in June 2023. Figure 24 shows the OBU integrated in the vehicle and connected through 5G to the network of Nokia in Ulm.

Figure 24: OBU integrated in the vehicle provided by Fivecomm and connected to a Quectel RM500Q-AE 5G UE

3.4.3. LINKS virtual OBUs

The virtual OBUs are based on VMs in which 5G-IANA specific far-edge services (i.e., the “Information and localization” service and the “Resource monitoring” service) are working as for real OBUs. Virtual OBUs can be used for initial testing of nApps and for

testing the deployment of the nApps through the 5G-IANA Platform. In the specific, the virtual OBUs can be used for software testing, but not for testing 5G network connectivity as they are in the same hardware environment of the other VMs of the 5G-IANA Platform.

The virtual OBUs have been instantiated in the 5G-IANA Environment to be reachable from the other VMs of the 5G-IANA Platform. The virtual OBUs have been integrated into the microk8s cluster by performing manually the join as for the case of the real OBUs. Being the virtual OBUs part the of the 5G-IANA Environment, it was possible to test on them the deployment of nApps by using the 5G-IANA AO.

3.4.3.1. *Nokia Testbed*

One Linux Kernel-based Virtual Machine (KVM) is configured on the 5G-IANA Server hardware. Two virtual machines to host the vOBUs used in the 5G-IANA project are installed with capabilities as listed in Table 7. The operating system Ubuntu server 22.04 LTS and Kubernetes are installed on this VM. The root rights are restricted to Nokia, i.e., any SW installation requiring root rights such as Kubernetes is realized by Nokia.

Hostname	CPU	Memory [GB]	NIC1	NIC2	vda [GiB]	vdb [GiB]
links-vobu-1	4	4	192.168.100.101	192.168.101.101	50	0
links-vobu-2	4	4	192.168.100.102	192.168.101.102	50	0

Table 7: VMs capacities on 5G-IANA Nokia platform for LINKS' virtual On-Board Units

The networking of the virtual machines and the access of the 5G-IANA platform are described in section 3.6. For further information on KVM, please refer to [5].

3.5. Additional Dependent System Tools

3.5.1. qMON Testing and Monitoring Tool

3.5.1.1. *Overview*

qMON is a set of network performance testing and monitoring tools integrated into a centrally managed product for mobile, fixed and cloud environments, while enabling zero data loss, end-to-end measurements, realistic load generation and testing, and

measuring/testing automation. It consists of several (logical) components: distributed autonomous agents (this component is also called qMON NetworkSensor, otherwise, for the sake of the simplicity, we will continue using general term qMON agent here), qMON Reference Server, centralized or distributed (i.e., to achieve redundancy) measurements results (KPIs) collector/database (qMON Collector), centralized cloud-based system management (qMON Manager), and real-time monitoring and advanced cloud-based analytics (qMON Insight component powered by either enterprise-ready MySQL/MSSQL tools or cloud-native Prometheus-based stack, both supporting Grafana, while advanced post-analytics is provided by Tableau). Measuring of more than 100 KPIs related to network, services, applications testing (DNS, ping, ftp UL, ftp/http DL, iperf udp/tcp, web, etc.), as well as mobile network and radio testing (e.g., RSSI, RSRP, SNIR, TxPower, etc.) is supported.

qMON agents are available integrated to certain mobile or fixed device (e.g., Samsung Galaxy Series mobile phone; lightweight mobile M2M client (e.g., RPi); or office/industrial PC platforms (such as iBase, Lenovo Tiny) as well as software client packaged as VNF, VM or Docker container. Tests and measurements are performed between agents or between the agent and a qMON Reference Server. The latter is typically deployed at some central location such as edge or central cloud, while agents are placed on various locations in the network (e.g., users' locations, locations where certain parts of distributed applications are executed).

3.5.1.2. qMON architecture for testbeds

Each slice deployed in the testbed requires its own independent testing and monitoring setup. For client-side testing, qMON agent will be deployed to a RPi which is further connected to the device providing 5G connectivity (e.g., RSU or OBU). Similarly, a qMON agent can be placed directly to the device as a container running on top of Kubernetes. On the other end of the slice (i.e., Edge), dedicated VM running a qMON Reference Server will be deployed to enable required test and validation cases. As well, another dedicated VM is required to deploy a qMON agent. Same architecture will be replicated for each single slice in the testbed.

Data collected by qMON agents will be forwarded to qMON Collector located at Internet Institute cloud. At the ININ cloud, qMON Management and analytics/insight tools will be deployed as well. There is a VPN tunnel established between Nokia testbed, TS testbed, and ININ cloud (see section 3.5.1.4 for implementation details). Figure 25 depicts the

above-described architecture and additionally shows a couple of possible testing flows in the testbed:

1. network services testing (e.g., DNS),
2. reference services and performance testing (e.g., web response, throughput, RTT, packet loss, jitter),
3. public services test (e.g., web response from google.com).

Figure 25: qMON architecture for 5G-IANA testbeds and possible testing flows: (1.) network services testing, (2.) reference services and performance testing, (3.) public services test

3.5.1.3. Technical specifications

As previously explained in section 3.5.1.2, each slice at every testbed requires two dedicated VMs for deploying qMON software to enable required test and validation cases (i.e., qMON Reference Server and qMON Agent). Minimum requirements for a VMs are as follows (see also sections 3.5.1.5 and 3.5.1.6 for further details on current implementation):

- qMON Reference server VM:
 - vCPU: 4
 - RAM: 8 GB
 - Storage: 40 GB disc space
 - OS: Ubuntu 18,
- qMON agent VM:
 - vCPU: 2
 - RAM: 4 GB

- Storage: 40 GB disc space,
- OS: Ubuntu 18.

On the client side, qMON agents are commonly deployed/integrated to certain mobile or fixed device. In 5G-IANA testbeds, the preferred option will be qMON agent deployed to a RPi which is further connected to the device providing 5G connectivity (e.g., RSU or OBU). Requirements for the RPi are as follows:

- RPi4
- RAM: 4GB
- sd card: 32GB

Depending on the test performed, network connections allowing for protocols under test need to be established (e.g., not blocked by a firewall) between the qMON agents, reference server(s) and other (application) servers involved in testing/monitoring scenarios (e.g., see section 3.5.1.1 for additional information on application protocols available for testing purposes).

3.5.1.4. Initial implementation

At this stage (as depicted in Figure 26), qMON Reference Server and qMON agent software respectively have been deployed to two separate VMs in Nokia testbed. qMON agent has been also deployed in TS lab network to perform initial test related to cross-border connectivity provided by site-to-site VPN between the Nokia and Telekom Slovenija testbeds (see results below). Another qMON agent has been deployed in the ININ environment - this agent serves for reference only.

Figure 26: Initial qMON implementation scheme

Following tests have been performed (mean result values presented):

- Download (data transfer from Nokia to Telekom Slovenije): 202 Mbit/s (see Figure 26 for details),
- Upload (data transfer from Telekom Slovenije to Nokia): 207 Mbit/s (see Figure 26 for details),
- RTT: 16.2 ms (see Figure 27 for details).

Figure 27: Download and Upload cross-border measurements between Telekom Slovenije and Nokia testbeds

Figure 28: Round Trip Time (RTT) cross-border measurements between Telekom Slovenije and Nokia testbeds (green color)

3.5.1.5. Nokia Testbed

One Linux Kernel-based Virtual Machine (KVM) is configured on the 5G-IANA Server hardware (see also section 3.2.2). Two virtual machines to host the qMON Reference Server and qMON agent are installed with capabilities as listed in Table 8. The operating system Ubuntu server 22.04 LTS and Kubernetes are installed on this VM. The root rights are restricted to Nokia, i.e., any SW installation requiring root rights such as Kubernetes is realized by Nokia.

Hostname	CPU	Memory [GB]	NIC1	NIC2	vda [GiB]	vdb [GiB]
5G-iana-qmon-server	4	8	192.168.100.8	-	50	50
5G-iana-qmon-agent	2	8	192.168.100.9	-	50	50

Table 8: VMs capacities on 5G-IANA Nokia platform for qMON

The networking of the virtual machines and the access of the 5G-IANA platform is described in section 3.6.

3.5.1.6. Telekom Slovenije Testbed

On top of the physical server infrastructure described in the section 3.2.1.2, two virtual machines to host the qMON Reference Server and qMON agent are installed with capabilities as listed in Table 9. The operating system Ubuntu server 20.10 and Kubernetes are installed on this VM.

Hostname	CPU	Memory [GB]	NIC1	NIC2	Iv [GiB]
host1 - production	4	8	192.168.178.191	-	100
host2 - currently used for development purposes only	4	8	192.168.178.192	-	100

Table 9: VMs capacities for qMON within Telekom Slovenia testbed

3.6. 5G-IANA Networking

This section discusses the connections and subnetworks, which are established in 5G-IANA. The 5G System is used to provide a physical connection between smart phones, OBUs and RSUs with MEC-Servers or with the Internet (and the Cloud-Servers located in the Internet). Once the physical connection is established, the smart phones, OBUs and RSUs become connected to subnetworks for application data distribution and 5G-IANA network administration. Finally, the VPN connections between 5G-IANA partners and the testbeds is described.

3.6.1. Nokia Testbed

Figure 29 summarizes the networks formed to connect the 5G-IANA components.

Figure 29: 5G-IANA Project Networking Overview

3.6.1.1. 5G System (5GS) Connectivity (5GS Internal Transport Network)

As outlined in section 2.1.5, two network slices are configured in the Nokia testbed: a V2X slice and an eMBB slice. On the EDGE Server (see section 2.1.2), two Data Networks (DN) are configured:

- The DN with the Data Network Name (DNN) ulmas5qi79 terminates the V2X slice. Within the Nokia 5G System, this DN has the IP address 10.47.194.249.
- The DN with the Data Network Name (DNN) ulmas5qi7 terminates the eMBB slice. Within the Nokia 5G System, this DN has the IP address 10.47.194.248.

Figure 30: Physical Connection between the UE and the Data Networks

In Figure 30, the 5GS connectivity is shown in green. Note that these IP addresses may change, however any change does not affect the connectivity on application layer, which are described in the following two subsections.

3.6.1.1.1. Establishment of a V2X Connection

A V2X connection is established between the UE and the DN with the DNN **ulmas5qi79**. During the connection establishment, the UE gets a dynamic IP address from 10.47.54.0 to 10.47.55.255 allocated.

3.6.1.1.2. eMBB Connection

An eMBB connection is established between the UE and the DN with the DNN **ulmas5qi7**. During the connection establishment, the UE gets a static IP address allocated within following IP address range: 172.16.1.5 to 172.16.1.24. The static IP address is part of the user's subscription profile, which is identified by the used SIM card.

The use of a static IP address simplifies tracing and error detection within the Nokia test network. It also uniquely identifies a user in case of violation of data protection and data privacy regulations.

3.6.1.2. The subnets for transmission of eMBB application data and 5G-IANA administrative data

Two subnets have been defined:

- The subnet 192.168.101.0/24 links all virtual machines configured on the EDGE Server and the 5G-IANA platform.

- The subnet 192.168.201.0/24 links all virtual machines configured on the FAR EDGE Server and the virtual machine “Gateway” on the MEC-Server. The virtual machine “Gateway” connects the subnet 192.168.201.0/24 with subnet 192.168.101.0/24.

The two subnets should be used to distribute 5G-IANA management and control data, as well as for distributing application data which requires eMBB QoS from the 5GS.

The two subnets should be used for distributing application data which requires V2X QoS from the 5GS. The two subnets could be also used to distribute 5G-IANA management and control data, however this is not recommended.

A connection to the Internet via the Nokia ISP router and VPN server is supported.

In Figure 29, the subnetwork in the Nokia testbed for data flows requiring eMBB QoS is shown in blue lines and numbers.

3.6.1.3. The subnets for transmission of V2X application data

Two subnets have been defined:

- The subnet 192.168.100.0/24 links all virtual machines configured on the EDGE Server and the 5G-IANA platform.
- The subnet 192.168.200.0/24 links all virtual machines configured on the FAR EDGE Server and the virtual machine “Gateway” on the MEC-Server. The virtual machine “Gateway” connects the subnet 192.168.200.0/24 with subnet 192.168.100.0/24.

A connection to the Internet via the Nokia ISP router and VPN server is supported.

In Figure 29, the subnetwork in the Nokia testbed for data flows requiring V2X QoS is shown in red lines and numbers.

3.6.2. Telekom Slovenije Testbed

For the purpose of UC7, a network connection between TS and Nokia Testbeds is needed. This way the cross-border communication can be demonstrated and tested. The connection must be done through VPN tunnel to ensure proper security.

Figure 31: Cross border connection between Nokia's and Telekom Slovenije's testbed

With such network configuration the UC7 demonstration can include the seamless streaming of data from OBUs and RSUs across the border to approaching rescue vehicle. Firefighters and medical personnel can evaluate the data while they are still in the vehicle and are therefore losing less time on the location of the accident inside cross border tunnel.

3.6.3. VPN Tunnels to Access the Testbeds

Access to the Nokia Testbed:

WireGuard® is used as communication protocol to implement encrypted virtual private networks (VPNs) between the Nokia testbed and 5G-IANA partners. A WireGuard® Server is installed at the Nokia side and a WireGuard® client at each partner's side. Within

the VPN, the WireGuard® Server has the IP address 10.0.0.1, while a WireGuard® client has the address 10.0.0.x, whereby the integer value $x > 1$ is partner specific.

The UDP port number 51820 is used to signal that an IP packet arriving from the Internet at the WireGuard® Server carries an encrypted IP packet, which should be forwarded in the sub-network for 5G-IANA administration.

A WireGuard® client-server VPN connection has been provided to all 5G-IANA partners, who requested access to the Nokia Testbed.

Access to the Telekom Slovenije Testbed:

The Telekom Slovenije Testbed can be accessed in two different ways:

- TS can open access through the Telekom Slovenije firewall for partner IP address. Partner can then use SSH to deploy and configure software components.
- A VPN site-to-site tunnel can be configured between partner and TS.

Access type can be selected based on partner's preferences or on specific requirements.

Connectivity between the Nokia and Telekom Slovenije testbeds:

An IPsec VPN platform for Linux was installed, which is used to establish a site-to-site VPN connection between the Nokia and the Telekom Slovenije testbed. In Telekom Slovenije, subnet 192.168.178.0/24 is used for 5G-IANA management and control information, while subnet 192.168.179.0/24 is used for application related data transmission.

Figure 32: VPN Connections

4. CONCLUSION

The Nokia and Telekom Slovenije 5G Systems were upgraded to provide stable and reliable 5G SA connectivity for a range of automotive services to be deployed on the 5G-IANA experimentation platforms. The activities included:

- the provision of a latency optimised 5G V2X slice and an eMBB network slices in Nokia testbed. In low cell load scenarios, both slices support a round-trip-time of less than 20ms. In high cell load scenarios, the higher priority V2X slice is currently guaranteed a minimum of 70% of the cell capacity and the lower priority eMBB slice a minimum of 10%.
- the provision of a testing site and the on-site 5G network capabilities: for instance, at the dedicated parking lot for UC testing near one of the antenna sites of the Nokia testbed, UL throughput rates of at least 7Mbps and DL throughput rates of at least 100Mbps are provided.
- intensive testing of 5G smartphones and 5G modems to ensure they operate stable and support the 5G-IANA use cases.
- the support of partners related to any 5G connectivity problems with their deployed 5G UEs, before and during UC trials.
- the provision of VPN connectivity to the MEC-Server and the 5G-IANA platform hosted in the testbeds, and the support of partners related to any connectivity problems to the servers.

The integration of the 5G-IANA experimentation platform is divided into activities at Gitlab Servers, the 5G-IANA Platform Servers, the EDGE Servers, and the Far-Edge Devices.

A GitLab server hosts the source code and compiles the code.

The 5G-IANA platform is used the development, orchestration, and management of nApps. The 5G-IANA platform divides into following components, whereby for each component, its key tasks, its integration status, and its system requirements was described. The described components were:

- 5G-IANA Catalogue,
- 5G-IANA Composer,
- 5G-IANA Application Orchestrator (AO),
- 5G-IANA Slice Management (SM) and Resource Orchestration,
- 5G-IANA Monitoring, and

- 5G-IANA Distributed Machine Learning Orchestrator (DMLO).

In both the Nokia and Telekom Slovenije testbeds, a server was acquired which meets the combined system requirements of the 5G-IANA platform components. For each component, virtual machines were installed according to the component's system requirements and networked with all virtual machines hosting 5G-IANA components.

EDGE Servers provide cloud computing capabilities and an IT service environment for 5G-IANA nApps at the edge of the 5G System. Both in Nokia and Telekom Slovenije testbeds, a server was acquired which meets the 5G-IANA EDGE Server requirements. One virtual machine was installed to host the 5G-IANA EDGE Server which executes nApps.

Far-Edge Devices are OBU and RSUs, provided by LINKS and Fivecomm. Their computing capabilities, the used 5G radio modules, the deployment of microk8s clusters to run 5G-IANA nApps, and integration trials were presented. The microk8s clusters are networked with other virtual machines hosting 5G-IANA components. Additionally, virtual OBUs have been installed to allow early nApp testing and simulations with the simulator CARLA before conducting drive tests with OBUs in the testbeds.

An additionally used tool in the 5G-IANA experimentation platform is qMON, whose functionality was described.

All 5G-IANA components can be accessed by VPN and either updated or used in the nApp creation process. All components are networked to support the chain of activities to create, modify, launch, monitor, and decommission an nApp.

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